

COMPARING THE ROLE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF LAW IN TACKLING FINANCIAL CORRUPTION IN PAKISTAN AND U.K

Muhammad Usman Iqbal^{*1}, Dr. Lars Mossesson²

^{*1,2}St Mary's University, Twickenham, London. England

Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Usman Iqbal

Advocate High Courts of Pakistan

Panel Advocate of Legal Aid & Justice Authority under the Ministry of Human Rights of Pakistan

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15752248>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
04 May, 2025	04 June, 2025	17 June, 2025	27 June, 2025

ABSTRACT

This research offers a comparative analysis of anti-corruption laws in the United Kingdom and Pakistan, critically examining the legal frameworks, institutional mechanisms, and the effectiveness of their implementation. While Pakistan has enacted several strong legislations to combat financial corruption, this study finds that enforcement remains severely lacking, particularly in cases involving politically powerful and influential individuals, including the military. In contrast, the UK's model emphasizes transparency, independent oversight bodies, and accountability, resulting in a more functional and credible anti-corruption system. Drawing from legislative reviews, case law, and real-world examples, this paper argues that the core issue in Pakistan is not the absence of law but the failure to implement it. The article concludes with policy recommendations for Pakistan, including the need for stronger enforcement agencies, judicial independence, and increased public transparency. These reforms are essential not only to reduce corruption but also to restore public trust in state institutions.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 General Introduction: Corruption thrives in an opaque environment, particularly affecting vulnerable segments of society. Its consequences are immediate and extensive, obstructing access to healthcare and education, impeding infrastructure development, and diverting funds from essential initiatives. Corruption undermines trust between citizens and governments, hindering progress and exacerbating poverty.¹ Corruption severely impedes global social and economic growth, obstructing sustainable development, especially in disadvantaged communities. It hampers

corporate expansion, resulting in higher costs and legal risks that undermine profitability and reputation. Transaction costs rise due to illicit demands, reducing operational efficiency. Corruption distorts fair competition, favoring those involved and discouraging new entrants. It hinders long-term investments as corruption-related risks worry investors. In response, stricter anti-corruption laws have emerged globally, emphasizing the need for effective policies. Businesses must adopt anti-corruption measures to safeguard reputation, enhance stakeholder trust, and promote ethical conduct throughout their operations.² Pakistan regrettably holds a

¹ GEORGIEVA, K. 'Fighting corruption: the importance is crystal clear' (2018) World Bank Blogs. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/voices/fighting-corruption-importance-crystal-clear>

² Jamali, M. 'Anti-Corruption' United Nations Global Compact. <https://unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/our-work/governance/anti-corruption>

tragic reputation to be one of the most corrupt nations in the world within the international community of nations. Every aspect of Pakistani society has been infiltrated by corruption, and currently not a single government institution is immune to this lethal disease. The core pillars of our economy, such as initiatives for development, attractive jobs, finance from banks and write-offs, and supplier contracts, are all affected by massive corruption. The average citizen is impacted by the small-scale and middle-level corruption that he must deal with on a daily basis in government departments and businesses.³ Although there are serious issues that need to be resolved, corruption is not pervasive in the UK. The latest Corruption in the UK study from Transparency International's UK revealed problems with corruption in several of Britain's important industries and organizations. Recent scandals like those around political party finance, corruption in sports like cricket and phone hacking have further demonstrated the presence of the issue and the pressing need to confront it. The United Kingdom has victims of corruption, just like any other nation. Because they belong to socially excluded groups or because corruption often manifests itself in imperceptible ways, the victims of corruption may not be as readily evident in the UK. Sometimes corruption is illegal, while other times it is legal but wrong which could be seen by the MPs' expenditures scandal, which led to few charges.⁴

1.2 Research Objectives: Research objectives drive every aspect of the research process, ensuring focused data collection, argument construction, and conclusion development. They eliminate unnecessary research, facilitate strategy evaluation, and inform approach selection. Objectives demonstrate expertise, enhance techniques, and contribute to ongoing debates.⁵ The objectives of conducting this

³ Aqil, M. 'The cancer of corruption in Pakistan' (2023) Pakistan Observer. <https://pakobserver.net/the-cancer-of-corruption-in-pakistan-by-tariq-aqil/>

⁴ Transparency International UK 'Corruption and UK' Transparency International UK <https://www.transparency.org.uk/corruption-and-uk>

⁵ Ryan, E. 'Research Objectives | Definition & Examples' (2022) Scribbr.

research, by comparing anti-corruption efforts and situation in the UK and Pakistan, with a focus on financial corruption, are as follows:

1. Compare and analyze anti-corruption legislation in both countries.
2. Examine high-profile cases and outcomes related to financial corruption.
3. Assess strengths and weaknesses of Pakistan's anti-corruption initiatives.
4. Identify ideas from the UK to improve Pakistan's system.
5. Make recommendations to strengthen the fight against financial corruption in Pakistan.
6. Contribute to academic knowledge and provide useful information for policymakers and practitioners.

These research objectives guide the examination and analysis of anti-corruption measures in the UK and Pakistan, focusing on financial corruption and the potential improvements that can be adopted based on the UK's experiences.

1.3 Significance of Study: This study holds significant value as it examines the anti-corruption frameworks in Pakistan and the UK, with a focus on financial corruption. By comparing legislation, organizations, notable cases and overall situation in Pakistan, it provides crucial insights into their strengths and weaknesses. The study contributes to academic knowledge of anti-corruption initiatives and clarifies the efficacy of approaches in combating financial corruption. It offers practical benefits for policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders by identifying takeaways from the UK system to strengthen Pakistan's anti-corruption efforts. The study's conclusions guide changes in Pakistan's framework and help develop focused policies to reduce corruption and restore public confidence. Additionally, it aims to foster fair competition, attract investment, and improve societal well-being by combating financial corruption. In summary, this research significantly contributes to academia, offers

<https://www.scribbr.com/research-process/research-objectives/#:~:text=about%20research%20objective s- .What%20is%20a%20research%20objective%3Fen d%20of%20your%20problem%20statement.>

practical findings, influences policy, and promotes societal progress.

Methodology

2.1 Research approach: A comprehensive analysis of anti-corruption efforts in both countries will be conducted in this research, by focusing specifically on the unfortunate situation of financial corruption in Pakistan. The research approach will consist of both doctrinal legal research and comparative legal research methodologies. To examine the relevant legislation and laws to combat financial corruption, the doctrinal method of research will be used. This will involve a study of legal texts and statutes in both the countries. However, as aiming to compare the statistics and overall situation of financial corruption in Pakistan and the UK, comparative research methods will be used as primary research methods. This approach will allow to reveal the overall situation of financial corruption, similarities and differences in anti-corruption strategies, systems, and outcomes. By drawing insights from the UK's experiences and practices to get rid of corruption, this dissertation seeks to identify valuable takeaways along with the recommendations on concerned issues, which can contribute to improve the unfortunate situation of financial corruption in Pakistan.

2.2 Data collection methods:

To broadly address the anti-corruption laws in both the Pakistan and UK, relevant legislation from primary sources shall be approached. Such sources will help in understanding the legal frameworks that run anti-corruption efforts in both countries. In order to analyze the statistics of corruption, reliable and reputable organization's statistics, such as Transparency International and the World Justice Project will be approached to obtain reliable figures. This approach will provide valuable insights into the prevalence and impact of corruption in both countries. Additionally, to highlight major corruption cases and the overall situation of financial corruption in Pakistan, a variety of sources will be approached. As due to the sensitive nature of the topic, academic sources may have limited information available. In such case, sources including statements and interviews from relevant individuals as well as

relevant articles in multiple and leading newspapers will be approached. Moreover, interviews of relevant retired officials including judges and generals will be addressed to gain further understanding. In such references, it would be noticed that most journalists in Pakistan preferred to remain anonymous when breaking or revealing such news, and used the name of the newspaper on publication instead of their own, which highlights the challenging and sensitive nature of this research area.

It is noteworthy to mention here that all these statements, interviews and videos are publically available on multiple platforms and can be accessed by any individual.

Anti-Corruption Laws in Pakistan

3.1 Legislation on Anti-corruption laws in Pakistan: The primary legislations on anti-corruption laws in Pakistan are, but not limited to Prevention of Corruption Act, 1947, National Accountability Ordinance (NAO), 1999, Federal Investigation Agency Act, 1974, Anti-Corruption Establishment (ACE), and Benami Transactions (Prohibition) Act, 2017.

(i) **The Prevention of Corruption Act, 1947:** It is a significant law designed to combat corrupt behavior. It establishes a framework for prosecuting crimes of corruption, including bribery, theft, misuse of authority, and money laundering. Offenses falling under sections 161, 162, 163, 164, 165, and 165-A of the Pakistan Penal Code, as well as those who accept or seek to acquire expensive items in connection with their official duties without due consideration, are punishable under this Act. Pakistani nationals and government employees are subject to the Act's provisions, with potential penalties of up to seven years in prison, fines, or both. The Act aims to deter corruption, promote integrity in public service, and hold accountable those involved in illicit activities.⁶

(ii) **National Accountability Ordinance (NAO), 1999:**

⁶ Prevention of Corruption Act, 1947 (Act No. II of 1947)

https://ace.punjab.gov.pk/system/files/THE_PREVENTION_OF_CORRUPTION_ACT_1947.pdf

The National Accountability Bureau (NAB) in Pakistan is an independent federal entity led by Lt Gen (ret'd) Nazir Ahmed Butt. It strengthens anti-corruption efforts, conducts financial surveillance, and carries out operations against financial crimes. The NAB also conducts preventive and awareness campaigns, with the Prosecutor General of Accountability and the Chairman being main officials.⁷ The National Accountability Bureau (NAB) covers a wide range of offences related to illicit economic practices, financial crimes, and misuse of authority. Specific provisions in the NAB Ordinance address corruption, corrupt practices, embezzlement, theft of funds, and holding assets beyond one's means. Section 9 defines various acts and corrupt practices, including accepting or offering illegal compensation, acquiring valuable objects without proper consideration, misappropriation of property, acquisition of assets through corrupt means, abuse of power, and issuance of directives for personal gain. Under section 9(b), bail is not granted for offences under this ordinance, and cases may be closed upon the Chairman's finding of no prima facie evidence under section 9(c). Penalties for corruption and corrupt practices include up to 14 years of rigorous imprisonment and forfeiture of disproportionate assets mentioned in section 10. Section 11 ensures penalties are proportionate to the financial gain from the offence. Section 12 grants NAB the power to freeze assets during investigations to protect them from misuse.⁸ The NAB law aims to deter corruption, promote transparency, and foster accountability through strict penalties. It restores public confidence, boosts investor trust, and ensures efficient utilization of public resources for societal progress.

(iii) **Federal Investigation Agency Act, 1974:** The Anti-Corruption Wing of the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) addresses organized

crimes nationally, including human trafficking and terrorism. It monitors cases related to counterfeit currency, intellectual property rights, and theft of oil, gas, and electricity, spurious drugs, and offences against the Human Organ Transplant Act. It responds to complaints from various entities including the Prime Minister and National Assembly, ensures regular updates, and selects FIA officials to participate in important committees and meetings of the National Assembly.⁹ The FIA operates under Pakistan Penal Code and special laws, which encompass 115 provisions and 33 sections, including those in the Prevention of Corruption Act, 1947. It is worth noting that the FIA Act of 1974 primarily applies to federal government agencies, enterprises, and organizations.¹⁰

(iv) **Anti-corruption Establishment:** The adoption of the West Pakistan Anti-Corruption Establishment Ordinance in 1961 played a crucial role in the fight against corruption. It abolished the Sindh Prevention of Bribery and Corruption Act and established a specialized institution to investigate corruption offenses involving provincial public workers in West Pakistan. While Sindh and Balochistan have introduced their own anti-corruption legislation, the West Pakistan Anti-Corruption Establishment Ordinance remains in effect in Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). The ACEs are managed by officers from various backgrounds, overseeing employees of provincial government departments, companies, and organizations.¹¹

(v) **Benami Transactions (Prohibition) Act, 2017:** The Government of Pakistan implemented the "Benami Transactions (Prohibition) Act, 2017" to criminalize holding benami property and enhance transparency in property transactions. Benami transactions involve property held by one person while the

⁷ Wikipedia, 'National Accountability Bureau' Wikipedia.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Accountability_Bureau

⁸ National Accountability Bureau Ordinance 1999 (NAB Ordinance), No. XIX of 1999. <https://nab.gov.pk/Downloads/nao.asp>

⁹ Federal Investigation Agency, 'Anti-Corruption Wing Mandate' Federal Investigation Agency. <https://fia.gov.pk/acw#:~:text=%C3%97-.Field%20Formation,government%20public%20servants%20and%20funds>.

¹⁰ Sadiq, E. 'Anti-Corruption investigation agencies in Pakistan' (2020). <https://issrapapers.ndu.edu.pk/site/article/view/51/26>

¹¹ Ibid

consideration is provided by another, intending to benefit the person who provided the consideration. The Act covers all types of assets and imposes penalties of imprisonment and fines for acquiring or possessing benami property. Certain individuals, such as fiduciaries and specified family members, are exempt from prosecution under this Act.¹²

3.2 Legislation on Anti-corruption laws in U.K: The primary legislation on anti-corruption is but not limited to, Bribery Act 2010, Criminal Finances Act 2017, Fraud Act 2006, and Proceeds of Crime Act 2002.

(i) **Bribery Act 2010:** The UK Bribery Act of 2010 is the primary legislation in the United Kingdom for combating corruption. It has a wide scope, covering bribery in both public and private sectors. The Act applies to individuals, organizations, and residents of the UK, including those conducting business abroad. It highlights two major offenses: bribery of foreign public officials and failure of commercial organizations to prevent bribery. Organizations can protect themselves from prosecution by implementing "adequate procedures" to prevent bribery.¹³ The Bribery Act 2010 is a legislative act in the UK aimed at combating bribery and corruption. It provides a comprehensive framework, covering specific offenses, penalties, and defenses related to bribery. Section 1 establishes the offense of offering or giving a bribe, while Section 2 addresses offenses by bribery recipients. Section 6 prohibits bribery of foreign public officials, and Section 7 deals with the failure of commercial organizations to prevent bribery. Penalties for offenses under Sections 1, 2, 6, and 7 are established in Section 11. Section 13 offers

a defense for individuals charged with specific bribery offenses in certain circumstances.¹⁴

(ii) **Criminal Finances Act, 2017:** The Criminal Finances Act, effective from September 30, 2017, holds companies accountable for facilitating tax evasion. The offense occurs when a relevant body fails to prevent its representative from facilitating tax evasion. The penalty is a potentially unlimited financial penalty. HMRC provides compliance guidelines, including risk assessment, due diligence, prevention procedures, monitoring, communication, and top-level commitment.¹⁵ The Criminal Finances Act, 2017, effective from April 27, 2017, introduces significant modifications to civil recovery, money laundering, and enforcement authorities regarding terrorist property. It creates a new corporate crime of failing to stop the support of tax evasion. The Act is divided into four parts: Part 1 focuses on criminal proceeds, enforcement powers, money laundering, and civil recovery; Part 2 broadens asset recovery and money laundering authorities; Part 3 introduces two new corporate offences related to tax evasion support; Part 4 covers minor modifications and associated changes to relevant laws. It establishes "Unexplained Wealth Orders" under Part 1, Sections 1 to 9, allowing the explanation of disproportionate assets. Provisions for disclosure orders in money laundering investigations are added. HMRC and Financial Conduct Authority gain civil recovery powers. Sections 45 and 46 of Part 3 define corporate offences for failing to stop tax evasion support. Adequate preventive measures serve as a defense against these offences.¹⁶

¹² Aga Faquir Mohammad & Co. 'BENAMI TRANSACTIONS LAWS IN PAKISTAN' (2023). Pakistan Lawyers. <https://pakistanlawyer.com/articles/story/benami-transaction-laws-in-pakistan>

¹³ Dow Jones. 'What is United Kingdom Bribery Act?' Dow Jones. <https://www.dowjones.com/professional/risk/glossary/anti-bribery-corruption/uk-bribery-act/>

¹⁴ Bribery Act, 2010. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/23/contents>

¹⁵ Morton, M. 'Criminal Finances Act 2017: Failure to prevent facilitation of tax evasion' (2022). Mercia. <https://www.mercia-group.com/mercianews-and-blog/criminal-finances-act-2017/#:~:text=The%20Criminal%20Finances%20Act%20came,from%20criminally%20facilitating%20tax%20evasion.>

¹⁶ Smyth, E. 'Criminal Finances Act 2017' (2017) Kingsley Napley. <https://www.kingsleynapley.co.uk/insights/blogs/criminal-law-blog/criminal-finances-act-2017>

(iii) **Fraud Act, 2006:** The Fraud Act (2006) is a law applicable to the UK, dividing fraud into three categories: fraud by abuse of position, fraud by false representation, and fraud by failure to disclose information. Offenders may face fines or imprisonment, with a maximum of six months or 10 years depending on the conviction.¹⁷ The Fraud Act of 2006 defines fraud in Section 1, encompassing abuse of position, false representation, and failure to disclose facts. Penalties vary depending on the conviction, with imprisonment or fines applicable. Section 2 deals with fraud by false representation, Section 3 relates to failure to disclose information, and Section 4 addresses misuse of position. Section 7 covers the offense of producing or supplying items for fraud, and Section 9 deals with participation in fraudulent business operations. Section 11 covers the illicit act of receiving services dishonestly. Penalties may include imprisonment or fines based on the conviction.¹⁸

(iv) **Proceeds of Crime Act 2002:** The statute covers various offenses, including tax evasion, money laundering, theft, and fraud. It offers investigators multiple options for probing suspicious financial conduct. The Proceeds of Crime Act gave rise to the Assets Recovery Agency, responsible for tackling significant financial crime in the UK. This Act allows the seizure of unlawfully acquired property and also permits the seizure of indirectly obtained assets, even if acquired lawfully. It enables asset freezing, forfeiture, and money recovery, promotes information sharing, and establishes a financial intelligence unit to combat money laundering.¹⁹ The Proceeds of Crime Act of

2002 outlines key offences related to using illegally obtained financial gains. Sections 327 to 329 of part 7 prohibit various activities involving unlawful assets, with decreasing severity. The maximum sentence for all three offences is 14 years in jail. Section 327, "concealing," includes actions like hiding or altering proceeds of crime, including money laundering. Section 328 defines the "arrangements offence," involving participating in arrangements that aid in retaining or using illicit assets for others.²⁰

Unveiling Corruption: Comparative Analysis and Key Factors.

4.1 Corruption index comparison: Pakistan and the United Kingdom

Corruption index of Pakistan: According to perceptions index 2024 released by Transparency International, out of a total of 180 nations, Pakistan unfortunately, is ranked as the 135th, one of the most corrupt country. Pakistan's corruption ranking has fluctuated between 1995 and 2022, average 112th. 2005 saw the highest level of corruption, with a score of 144th, while 1995 saw the lowest score of at 39th.²¹ From 117th in 2018 to 140th in 2021, Pakistan's rating on the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) got worse. According to the report of Transparency International on corruption in Pakistan, the new government must guard against political scandals impeding all-encompassing anti-corruption initiatives. The report emphasizes the need for swift action and a strong anti-corruption strategy that stops illegal cash flows while preserving public space. It goes on to say that misusing, embezzling, or stealing from the public funds, may harm the same institutions in charge of safeguarding citizens, enforcing the law, and keeping the peace. The report's results show a clear link between

¹⁷ Counter Fraud Services. 'The Fraud Act (2006)' HSC Counter Fraud and Probity Services. <https://cfps.hscni.net/information/the-fraud-act/>

¹⁸ Fraud Act 2006. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2006/35/contents>

¹⁹ ID Now. 'Proceeds of Crime Act (POCA)' ID Now. <https://www.idnow.io/glossary/proceeds-of-crime-act-poca/#:~:text=The%20Proceeds%20of%20Crime%20Act%20allows%20for%20the%20confiscation%20of,indirectly%20derived%20from%20criminal%20activity.>

²⁰ Binns, J. 'A Simple Guide to the Law on Money Laundering under the Proceeds of Crime Act 2002' (2021) BCL Solicitors LLP. https://www.bcl.com/a-simple-guide-to-the-law-on-money-laundering-under-the-proceeds-of-crime-act-2002/?utm_source=mondaq&utm_medium=syndication&utm_term=Criminal-Law&utm_content=articleoriginal&utm_campaign=article

²¹ Trading Economics. 'Pakistan Corruption Rank' Trading Economics. <https://tradingeconomics.com/pakistan/corruption-rank>

conflict, corruption, and security since criminal and terrorist organizations frequently take advantage of the collusion of dishonest politicians, judges, law enforcement officers, and other public officials in order to operate unchecked.²²

Corruption index of U.K: In a ranking of 180 nations issued by Transparency International for 2024, the United Kingdom came in at number 20 overall.²³ Since it was rated in 11th place in 2021, it has dropped by nine spots. The score is based on information gathered from eight independent sources, including the World Economic Forum and the Economist Intelligence Unit.²⁴ Britain's repute has been harmed by a slew of political scandals inside the Conservative party. Consecutive departure of three prime ministers in 2022, leave a great impact, notably Boris Johnson after the Party gate affair. The report by transparency international drew attention to a long variety of issues, including the contentious awarding of contracts to Conservative Party supporters and the recruitment of people with political ties to positions in the public sector during the epidemic. These controversies have damaged Britain's reputation and highlight the need for more accountability and openness in the democratic system.²⁵

However, The Corruption Perceptions Index comparison between Pakistan and the United Kingdom illustrates the unfortunate and alarming situation in Pakistan and demonstrates a significant discrepancy. Pakistan is at 135th out of 180 countries, therefore it is clear that

corruption is a major problem. The United Kingdom, on the other hand, gains a considerably great position at 18th rank, highlighting a significant distinction between the two nations. This discrepancy highlights the severity of the problem in Pakistan and the urgent need for comprehensive anti-corruption measures to solve the issues it confronts. The rankings serve as a reminder of the necessity of giving transparent government and effective enforcement priority in order to effectively combat corruption. The statistics represent the regrettable reality of the corruption environment in Pakistan.

4.2 Financial corruption overview: Corporate and political realms, highlighting the Malik Riaz Hussain case:

One of the recent mega financial corruption case by a business tycoon, the investigations of which started in the UK by NCA and the money recovered in the result of a civil settlement and handed over to government of Pakistan, was a test case for anti-corruption laws and authorities of both the countries when it comes to the accountability of influential business tycoons.

Background of case:

Following an NCA investigation into "dirty money," a settlement led to the seizure of Malik Riaz Hussain, a Pakistani property tycoon, and his assets, valued at over £190 million. One of the confiscated properties is a £50 million home in London that has a view of Hyde Park. The proprietor of Bahria Town, known as Asia's largest private property developer, Malik Riaz Hussain, was accused of using money obtained via illegal means. In response, the UK's National Crime Agency (NCA) obtained nine orders freezing accounts totaling £140 million. The ownership of the house in central London as well as the sizeable money which was given to the Pakistani government. Notably, this is the biggest amount ever recovered by NCA in a civil settlement.²⁶ An official updated was uploaded

²² Ahmed, A. 'Pakistan's corruption score worst in a decade: report' (2023). The express Tribune. <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2398583/pakistans-corruption-score-worst-in-a-decade-report>

²³ Transparency International. "Our Work in United Kingdom" (2024) Transparency International. <https://www.transparency.org/en/countries/united-kingdom>

²⁴ Duncan, G. 'UK falls to its lowest ranking on global corruption index' (2023). The National News. <https://www.thenationalnews.com/world/uk-news/2023/01/31/uk-falls-to-its-lowest-ranking-on-global-corruption-index/>

²⁵ Lawson, A. 'UK drops down global corruption index after string of scandals' (2023). The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2023/jan/31/uk-global-corruption-index-transparency-international-qatar-russia-brazil>

²⁶ Jolly, J. 'Pakistani tycoon agrees to hand over £190m to UK authorities' (2019) The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2019/dec/03/pakistani-tycoon-malik-riaz-hussain-hands-over-pounds-190m-to-uk-authorities-nca->

by NCA on their official account which is following

https://twitter.com/NCA_UK/status/1201795020518506496. It is alleged that later, ex P.M Imran Khan's Cabinet discussed the matter concerning real estate tycoon Malik Riaz Hussain and his family on December 3, 2019. Approximately £140 million was repatriated to Pakistan but ended up in the Supreme Court's account against fines of 460 Billion Rupees, which was imposed on Malik's housing society by Supreme Court, instead of the national treasure, raising questions about the proper destination of the funds. Malik Riaz Hussain, the proprietor of the Private Housing Society, in exchange for Imran Khan, a former prime minister, establishing a trust for the Al-Qadir University Project. Within a few weeks after making this decision, the housing society agreed to donate to the institution, and the projected Al-Qadir University. Private Housing Society promised to pay for all startup and ongoing costs. Zulfi Bukhari, a really close friend of ex P.M Imran Khan received land in Jhelum that the housing society had acquired and given to him. Later, Zulfi Bukhari and Zaheer ud Din Babar Awan were expelled from the trust. An updated trust deed allowed for the relocation of the trust's office to Imran Khan's Banigala House. Between January 2021 and December 2021, donations of Rs 180 million were made to the Al-Qadir Trust. The settlement of £190 million under the PTI administration and the Private Housing Society's transfer of 458 acres of land to Al-Qadir Trust University are both under investigation by the National Accountability Bureau. Another allegation is that despite being set up as a trust, the Al-Qadir University Trust Project still charges tuition to its students while it waits for a grant to become a degree-granting institution. The Al-Qadir Trust's costs are exclusively the responsibility of housing society of Malik Riaz Hussain.²⁷

The National Crime Agency (NCA) in the UK demonstrated commendable transparency and integrity in their investigation into the corruption case of "dirty money" involving Malik Riaz Hussain. They diligently seized his

²⁷ The Nation. 'Al-Qadir Trust case - a timeline' (2023) The Nation. <https://www.nation.com.pk/09-May-2023/al-qadir-trust-case-a-timeline>

assets, including a valuable property, and returned the funds to the Pakistani government. In contrast, it is alleged that Pakistan's handling of the case was marred by corruption, as the repatriated funds were diverted to the Supreme Court's account as adjustment against fines imposed on Malik Riaz Hussain by Supreme Court instead of the national treasure. This highlights the need for stronger measures against corruption and a commitment to transparency and accountability in dealing with high-profile cases involving influential individuals and businesses.

Additionally, the alleged involvement of real estate tycoon Malik Riaz Hussain in several controversies has highlighted his power and its influence on journalists. The planned nature of an interview on Dunya News (famous Pakistani News Channel) with Malik Riaz was exposed in a behind-the-scenes video that was leaked a few years back and available all over the internet, demonstrating how two famous and influential journalists were following his instructions on each and every interview question. In the video, a male journalist can be seen demanding with Malik Riaz for a luxury home, citing the fact that other well-known journalists have gotten similar presents. This demonstrates how his power spread as he reportedly controlled journalism by giving journalists gifts and financial incentives.²⁸ Property tycoon Malik Riaz even acknowledged openly the widespread culture of bribery and corruption during an interview with well-known journalist Saleem Safi on Geo TV. Riaz acknowledged that it is necessary to bribe the appropriate authorities in order to complete any task or make a business successful.²⁹

4.3 Financial corruption in government institutions like judiciary and police: The government institutions primarily police and judiciary are of utmost importance in a country's

²⁸ Hamid Yusufzai, 'LEAKED Planted Interview Of Malik Riaz With Mehar Bukhari And Mubashir LuQman on Dunya TV FULL' (YouTube Video, Hamid Yusufzai, 14 June 2012) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ME2YirSD5cA>

²⁹ Future Investments, 'Malik Riaz Exclusive Interview with Saleem safi' (YouTube Video, Future Investments, 26 December 2018) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wwWmwNFoQTQ>

functioning. The judiciary upholds the rule of law, safeguards individual rights, and resolves disputes impartially. It ensures justice is served and maintains trust in the legal system. Meanwhile, the police maintain law and order, protect citizens, and deter crime. Their presence instills a sense of security and contributes to a stable society. Together, they are crucial pillars in preserving law, order, and justice within a country.

Unfortunately, the police and judiciary are declared as the most corrupt institutions in Pakistan, according to Transparency International Pakistan's National Corruption Perception Survey 2021. The report, which was published on December 8, 2021, identifies low incomes, weak accountability, and the greed of influential people as the root causes of corruption. The healthcare sector went on to become the fourth most corrupt, according to the survey. Overall, the report reveals that corruption in the public sector is higher, with the judiciary, the police, and contracting or tendering being the three most corrupt government sectors.³⁰

The same situation was repeated in 2022, as according to Transparency International Pakistan's National Corruption Perception Survey in December 2022 reveals that Judiciary, Police, contracting, health and education sectors remains the most corrupt government institutions of Pakistan. The report further highlighted a lack of confidence in the top anti-corruption entities, such as the National Accountability Bureau (NAB) as people found it ineffective in combating corruption at the national level in Pakistan.³¹ As far as judiciary is concerned, a judge of the Supreme Court of Pakistan receives a monthly salary of 18 lac Rupees, which includes a sizable salary, house rent, luxury vehicles, drivers, petrol, a daily travel allowance and discounted plane tickets. It

is disheartening and deeply regrettable that this is the stark reality in a nation that is underdeveloped and poor. The chief justice and other judges of higher courts receive approximately 10 lac Rupees per month, claims an unnamed senior official from the ministry of law and justice. The judges, including the chief justice, are also entitled to a Superior Judicial Allowance of 4.5 lac Rupees per month³² Even though these salaries and perks are super high to a citizen of Pakistan still the outcome is really concerning as according to the World Justice Project Pakistan ranks 129th out of 140 countries in rule of law, with civil justice ranked 125th and criminal justice ranked 97th out of 140 countries. In civil justice, the factors contributing to this low ranking include limited access and affordability (134th), corruption (110th), delays (104th), and ineffective enforcement (122nd). In criminal justice, the factors include ineffective criminal investigation (113th), lack of impartiality (124th), corruption (104th), and shortcomings in due process and rights of the accused (121st). These rankings highlight the challenges and deficiencies within Pakistan's judiciary system in terms of corruption and overall effectiveness.³³ It is alleged that the courts in Pakistan, sadly, operate with unfairness and inequality. Corruption permeates the entire process, favoring the rich over the poor. Bribery is normalized among corrupt government officials in the judiciary, hindering access to justice. The poor cannot even seek help from the police without filling the pockets with bribe. Consequently, they are forced to settle disputes with the wealthy. Even if they approach the court, the wealthy can bribe judicial officials for special treatment and documents, ensuring favorable outcomes. Unlike many countries, Pakistan's judicial system is flawed, displaying a clear bias towards those with money and resources.³⁴

³⁰ Abbasi, A. 'Police and judiciary most corrupt institutions, says TI Pakistan' (2021) The news International. <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/915055-police-and-judiciary-most-corrupt-institutions-says-ti-pakistan>

³¹ The express Tribune. 'Police, judiciary top most corrupt in Pakistan' (2022) The Express Tribune. <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2390359/police-judiciary-top-most-corrupt-in-pakistan-survey>

³² Geo-Fact Check. 'Fact-check: What are the salaries, benefits of the Supreme Court judges?' (2023) Geo TV. <https://www.geo.tv/latest/480211-fact-check-what-are-the-salaries-benefits-of-the-supreme-court-judges>

³³ World Justice Project. 'Pakistan' (2022). World Justice Project. <https://worldjusticeproject.org/rule-of-law-index/country/2022/Pakistan/>

³⁴ Pakistan Lawyer. 'Why is Pakistan's judiciary system different for rich and poor' (2021). Pakistan

In my years of practice as a lawyer in district courts of Pakistan I daily witnessed that despite the relatively favorable salaries and benefits offered to personnel in the district judiciary of Pakistan, the system is plagued by widespread financial corruption, particularly in the form of bribery. Rather than the judges themselves, it is often their readers and clerks who wield significant influence and control over the proceedings. These individuals manipulate the system by accepting bribes in exchange for granting dates for the next hearing or providing photocopies of crucial documents pertaining to relevant cases. Unfortunately, one cannot fathom escaping this cycle of corruption without succumbing to bribery at every single hearing. This deeply ingrained practice undermines the integrity of the judiciary and hampers the delivery of fair and impartial justice in Pakistan. A significant and comprehensive research and report named as “This Crooked System” Police abuse and reforms in Pakistan, by Human Right Watch was released in September 2016, according to which the police corruption and its underlying issues pose significant challenges in Pakistan. Influenced by powerful figures, the police often demand bribes before registering complaints. Citizens without political or financial influence struggle to file First Information Reports due to the high cost of bribe or fear of later on harassment. When it comes to salaries and funds, the situation of police is different from judiciary as according to senior police official, organizational shortcomings, inadequate training, limited resources, and poor working conditions hinder transparency and accountability. Financial constraints impede the proper functioning of the police, affecting their ability to provide welfare, facilities, and transportation.³⁵

When examining the rule of law in the UK, which relies heavily on the judiciary and law enforcement agencies, it is noteworthy that

Lawyer, access to Justice.
<https://pakistanlawyer.com/articles/story/why-is-pakistans-judiciary-system-different-for-rich-and-poor>

³⁵ Human Rights Watch. ‘The Crooked System, Police abuse and reforms in Pakistan’ (2016). Human Rights Watch
https://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/report_pdf/pakistan0916_web.pdf

according to the World Justice Project's rankings for 2024, the UK holds the impressive overall 15th position out of 142 countries in terms of its adherence to the rule of law by positioning at 21 out of 142 countries in delivering civil justice and at 18 out of 142 countries in delivering criminal justice. In contrast, Pakistan ranks significantly lower at 129th out of 142 countries in the same year. Such a significant disparity in rankings makes it unfair to draw direct comparisons between the two countries. One of the primary reasons for this disparity is the notable absence of corruption in the United Kingdom, as evidenced by its impressive 13th position out of 142 countries. The UK distinguishes itself by ensuring that government officials in the executive, judicial, police, and military branches do not exploit public office for personal gain. Additionally, the UK excels in delivering fundamental rights, evident from its 14th position out of 142 countries. The country achieves this by upholding principles such as safeguarding freedom of opinion, expression, belief, and religion, effectively guaranteeing the right to life and security, equal treatment and absence of discrimination, and ensuring due process of the law and the rights of the accused. These factors collectively contribute to the UK's exemplary rule of law.³⁶ Unfortunately all of these factors are completely missing in Pakistan.

4.4 Analysis of some High-Profile Corruption Cases Involving Pakistani politicians:

Pakistan has a history of misusing public funds by politicians and officials for personal gain, hindering significant sectors like health and education due to resource mismanagement. The Panama Papers scandal revealed a large number of Pakistani politicians and officials holding offshore accounts and companies, leading to public outrage and demands for accountability. The allocation of public project contracts further exemplifies corruption, with lawmakers and their relatives receiving preferential treatment regardless of their capabilities, depriving more qualified businesses of

³⁶ World Justice Project. ‘United Kingdom’ (2024). WJP Rule of Law Index.
<https://worldjusticeproject.org/rule-of-law-index/country/2024/United%20Kingdom/>

opportunities.³⁷ A few mega financial corruption cases on politicians of Pakistan are following;

Rental Power Plant Reference: Raja Parvez Ashraf who was the prime minister of Pakistan from June 2012 until March 2013, and currently serving as speaker of National Assembly of Pakistan, was accused of taking commission and kickbacks from nine rental power projects. He was accused of abusing his power to obtain a higher down payment of around Rs 22 billion for these contracts. In 2009, when he was the minister of water and power, he allegedly abused his position by getting approval of a rise in the down payment for rental power firms from the P.M.'s cabinet and the Economic Coordination Committee. It was alleged that the committee was reportedly misled by the summary that was provided, which said that a 7 percent advance was unworkable and needed to be increased to 14 percent.³⁸ The National Accountability bureau filed 12 references against the ex P.M and current speaker of N.A assembly out of which he was acquitted in 6 till April 2022 due to lack of evidence.³⁹ Later on in September 2022, he got acquitted in 6 more references as court ruled that it has no jurisdiction anymore to hear these cases due to change in NAB laws.⁴⁰

³⁷ Pakistan & Gulf Economist. 'Cronyism and Corruption in Pakistan's Political and Economic Landscape' (2023). Pakistan & Gulf Economist. <https://www.pakistangulfeconomist.com/2023/03/19/cronyism-and-corruption-in-pakistans-political-landscape/>

³⁸ Naseer, T. 'Former PM Raja Pervez Ashraf acquitted in Sahiwal Rental Power Project case' (2020). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1565158>

³⁹ Fazal, S. 'Rental Power Plant case: Acquittal plea of all accused to be decided together' (2022). Business Recorder. <https://www.brecorder.com/news/40168563/rental-power-plant-case-acquittal-plea-of-all-accused-to-be-decided-together>

⁴⁰ The Express Tribune. 'Ashraf gets relief in six more RPP cases' (2022). The Express Tribune. <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2376472/ashraf-gets-relief-in-six-more-rpp-cases>

Hajj Corruption Case:

The Haj corruption scandal shook the national politics as well as the citizens of Pakistan between 2010 and 2012. The former federal minister for religious affairs was accused of engaging in the Hajj corruption scandal and responsible for significant losses. Hamid Saeed Kazmi, the federal minister for religious affairs, as well as D.G. Haj and the joint secretary for religious affairs were all charged for fraud, deceit, abuse of power, and inflicting losses to the national treasury and the general people. They were accused of charging high rent for substandard accommodations for Pakistani pilgrims in Makkah and receiving kickbacks from the deal. The federal minister and joint secretary received a 16-year jail term and a 40-year D.G. on 3 June 2016.⁴¹ Later in March 2017, the all three convicts who were punished with imprisonment and fine of 150 Million Rupees each, was acquitted by the Islamabad High Court.⁴²

Oil and Gas Regulatory Authority Scam:

With 82 Billion Rupees, one of the biggest corruption cases in Pakistan, involved Tauqeer Sadiq, the chairman of OGRA, along with two ex-Prime Ministers Syed Yousaf Raza Gillani and Raja Pervez Ashraf. NAB filed two references in the court in 2013 related to Sadiq's illegal appointment in 2009 and corruption within OGRA during his tenure. The accusations included illegal appointments, manipulation of gas distribution company share prices, manipulation of the unaccounted-for-gas benchmark, unauthorized issuance of 500 CNG station licenses by taking 3 lac Rs from each applicant, and increasing the profit of gas distribution companies while reducing government taxes. The case also involved Sadiq's alleged connection with investors who benefited from the manipulation of share prices. The

⁴¹ Asad, M. 'Haj corruption case: Former federal minister sentenced to 16 years in prison' (2016). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1262506>

⁴² Chaudhry, W. 'Former religious affairs minister acquitted in Hajj corruption case' (2017). Daily Times. <https://dailytimes.com.pk/22150/former-religious-affairs-minister-acquitted-in-hajj-corruption-case/>

Sadiq successfully fled to Dubai.⁴³ Both the ex-Prime Ministers were acquitted in March 2022 from the case for making the illegal appointment of the chairman.⁴⁴

National Insurance Company Scam:

Former PPP leader and Federal Minister of Commerce, Makhdoom Amin Fahim faced charges of purchasing overpriced land by abusing his power as minister in 2009, causing significant financial losses to the national treasure. Along with others, he and Salman Ghani, former secretary of ministry of commerce, faced charges for appointing Muhammad Ayaz Khan Niazi as National Insurance Company Limited's chairman, who bought 10 acres of land in Korangi, Karachi at inflated prices. The market price of land was 482 million Rupees but it was purchased for 900 million Rupees and 41 million Rupees were sent into the Fahim's bank account.⁴⁵ Ex-Minister Makhdoom Amin Fahim expired on 21st of November 2015 due to leukemia.

Ex-chairman NICL and others were tried and got sentenced for 7 years in jail in December 2018.⁴⁶ The same chairman in 2009, was involved in a massive scam worth over Rs 6 billion. A company called Messrs Privilege bought 803 kanals of land in Lahore from the National Insurance Company Limited for 1.68 billion Rupees. Additionally, it was alleged that the NICL sold 20 kanals of land in Lahore to the same company for 1.7 billion Rupees. The price on which the land was sold was much lower than its market price due to which the country suffered loss of billions of Rupees but

⁴³ Dawn News. 'How the high-profile Ogra scam became a 'complicated' case' (2016). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1251360>

⁴⁴ Asad, M. 'NAB challenges acquittal of ex-PMs, others in Ogra chairman's appointment case' (2022). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1685905>

⁴⁵ The News International. 'PPP's Amin Fahim among 11 indicted in NICL scam case' (2015). The News International. <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/14621-ppps-amin-fahim-among-11-indicted-in-nicl-scam-case>

⁴⁶ The express Tribune. 'Ex-NICL chief, 5 others jailed over Rs490m corruption' (2018). The Express Tribune. <https://tribune.com.pk/story/1862685/former-chairman-five-others-imprisoned-nicl-corruption-case>

all the accused were acquitted in Land scam cases in 2020.⁴⁷

If we analyze the above mentioned cases of financial corruption, specifically those involving prominent politicians, a serious concerning repeated pattern emerges. In each of these and even in many other mega financial corruption cases which are publically available, the accused were initially held guilty by lower courts and punished. But a concerning repeated pattern becomes evident as we observe that on the appellate forums, they were repeatedly acquitted, raising serious concerns. This repeated pattern strengthens the unfortunate statistics regarding judiciary of Pakistan. The acquittals in these high-profile corruption cases highlight the need for a closer examination of the legal processes and mechanisms involved to ensure effective accountability and deterrence against financial corruption.

The executive branch, which ranks at 112 globally for officials abusing their positions, the judicial branch, which ranks at 112 due to similar abuses, the military and police, which rank poorly at 133 for abusing their positions, and the legislative branch, which ranks at 104 for officials abusing their positions, may all collectively be the contributing factors for failing in accountability of politicians.⁴⁸

On the contrary, it is noteworthy to highlight that a comprehensive examination of recent years' political landscape in the United Kingdom reveals a notable absence of such egregious cases of corruption involving politicians.

4.5 "Understanding the Causes of Corruption in Pakistan: Exploring Key Factors and Challenges":

When it comes to legislation, through strong legislation, anti-corruption laws in the UK and Pakistan aim to combat corruption. In Pakistan, the Prevention of Corruption Act, passed in 1947, prohibits many

⁴⁷ Daily Times. 'AC acquits former NICL head, co-accused in corruption case' (2020). Daily Times. <https://dailytimes.com.pk/533307/ac-acquits-former-nicl-head-co-accused-in-corruption-case/#:~:text=An%20accountability%20court%20on%20Saturday,tune%20of%20billions%20of%20rupees.>

⁴⁸ World Justice Project. 'Pakistan' (2024). World Justice Project. <https://worldjusticeproject.org/rule-of-law-index/country/2024/Pakistan/>

forms of corruption and imposes penalties including jail time and fines. The NAO, 1999, gives the National Accountability Bureau the authority to look into and prosecute cases of corruption and impose harsh fines on corrupt individuals, organizations and politicians. The Federal Investigation Agency Act, passed in 1974, aims to fight corruption, as well as human trafficking and cybercrime. Similarly, the UK has passed strong anti-corruption laws, such as the Bribery Act 2010, Criminal Finances Act 2017, and Proceeds of Crime Act 2002. The Bribery Act 2010 has extraterritorial jurisdiction and targets bribery in both the public and commercial sectors. It also requires organizations to prevent bribery. The Fraud Act 2006 focuses on fraud, the criminal Finances Act 2017 tackles financial offences, and the Proceeds of Crime Act 2002 addresses asset recovery from illicit acts. Even though the strict laws are there in Pakistan to beat the corruption just as U.K then why the situation is so worse in Pakistan? Following are the primary factors and challenges in the light of above provided statistics and material;

1. Weak Rule of Law: Despite the fact that there are strong laws against corruption, their application and enforcement in Pakistan are frequently weak and inefficient. Official data, such the Rule of Law Index from the World Justice Project, reflect this deficiency. Pakistan is ranked 129th out of 142 nations while the U.K is at 15th impressive position in the overall rule of law index, based on the most recent data of 2024. This weakness is linked to a number of things, including insufficient funding, a lack of expertise, and structural problems with the legal and law enforcement systems. The ineffective functioning of the organizations promotes an environment of impunity by allowing corrupt behavior to go unpunished.

2. Low Income and Resources in Government Institutes: Multiple articles by leading organizations, including "A Study of Economic, Cultural, and Political Causes of Police Corruption in Pakistan" published by

Oxford Academic,⁴⁹ "Police & Law Enforcement Reform in Pakistan: Crucial for Counterinsurgency and Counterterrorism Success" published by GSDRC,⁵⁰ "Inadequate resources affecting Punjab Police performance" published in Daily Times,⁵¹ and "Resource starved" published in The News,⁵² highlights the dire situation of government departments, particularly the police, in Pakistan due to low resources and incomes. These articles reveal unfortunate insights shared by senior police officials, highlighting the underfunded nature of the police and its impact on training and performance. Low incomes and insufficient resources can be significant causes of financial corruption, as officials resort to accepting bribes and engaging in corrupt practices to bridge the income gap and meet the department's resource needs. The scarcity of resources exacerbates the vulnerability of the police force to financial corruption.

3. Influence of Influential Persons: Upon reviewing the above mentioned cases with, their concerning outcomes on repeated patterns, media interviews, behind the scene leaked videos, and related articles, it appears that influential individuals have significant power and influence over the entire system in Pakistan. These influential figures might have the ability to manipulate institutions, control media narratives, and exert pressure on government officials due to their privileged status and connections. Unfortunately, such influence often leads to financial corruption such as

⁴⁹ Malik, N, 'A Study of Economic, Cultural, and Political Causes of Police Corruption in Pakistan' (2020). Oxford Academic. <https://academic.oup.com/policing/article/15/2/1446/5840664>

⁵⁰ Abbas, H, 'Police & Law Enforcement Reform in Pakistan: Crucial for Counterinsurgency and Counterterrorism Success' (2009). GSDRC. <https://gsdrc.org/document-library/police-law-enforcement-reform-in-pakistan-crucial-for-counterinsurgency-and-counterterrorism-success/>

⁵¹ Staff Report, 'Inadequate resources affecting Punjab Police performance' (2022). Daily Times. <https://dailytimes.com.pk/1013840/inadequate-resources-affecting-punjab-police-performance/>

⁵² Warraich, S, 'Resource starved' (2020). The News. <https://www.thenews.com.pk/tns/detail/603488-resource-starved>

normalizing bribes to get their illegal job done. The strong hold of these influential people creates an environment where corruption thrives, undermining the integrity and effectiveness of government institutions and fostering a culture of corruption.

4. Culture of Corruption: Despite receiving high salaries and perks in certain government institutions, especially as the judiciary, the World Justice Project ranks Pakistan's judiciary at 128 in civil justice and 98 in criminal justice out of 142 countries. Transparency International's National Corruption Perception Surveys consecutively ranks the judiciary as one of the most corrupt institutions in Pakistan. These findings highlight the extensive penetration of corruption throughout the country's social structure, leading to the normalization of dishonest behavior and creating a culture of corruption in Pakistan which is deeply ingrained and pervasive, affecting various aspects of society. Such culture of corruption poses a significant challenge to Pakistan's progress and undermines the trust of its citizens in public institutions.

5. Role of military: Since its founding in 1947, Pakistan has seen more than three decades of military dictatorship. Even when it isn't in power, the military continues to have a significant impact on politics and national security. The process of building democratic institutions and civilian command over the armed forces has been difficult, unclear, and fraught with failures. The military frequently finds civilian politicians who back them, weakening public confidence in government, undermining democracy, and enhancing their own authority. Long in control of Pakistani politics, the army disadvantages its rivals and stifles democracy. Politicians looking for quick ways to gain control have turned to the military, allowing the generals to dominate via division. While compromises are a necessary component of democracy, politicians must give civilian authority priority because it is the only right choice. Unfortunately, Pakistan's politicians have rewarded the military for violating election integrity, renegeing on their promise to democracy and raising concerns about its

viability.⁵³ The Military's involvement in politics was openly admitted by General Qamar Javed Bajwa, the head of Pakistan's armed forces, when he said in a speech in November 2022 that the military has historically intervened in political affairs. The General criticized the criticism on the military and admitted that it has been illegally interfering with politics for years. He did, however, made a crucial statement that from February of the previous year, the military is no longer intervening in political affairs. Bajwa called this transformation a "catharsis" for the military.⁵⁴ Apart from politics, the influence of the military on the Pakistani judiciary and the taking of decisions in accordance with their will by compromising the justice, has long been alleged, and it was even confirmed by an ex-chief justice of Pakistan, Justice Rtd. Nasim Hassan Shah, in an interview to famous senior journalist Iftikhar Ahmad on Geo T.V, by revealing that not every judge in Pakistan is courageous enough to sacrifice his job for fair justice and by saying "no" to the army so judges agree to do what the army instructs them to do.⁵⁵ Former Justice Shaukat Aziz Siddiqui made a significant speech at the Rawalpindi Bar Association in which he addressed the serious compromising of justice by judges. Ex-Justice highlighted how judges in the past damaged the country by compromising on justice and deciding cases in accordance with army instructions. Justice Siddiqui specifically referred to the controversial case of Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's execution as a result the military wanted to achieve. He alleged that the army and intelligence agencies had effectively taken over the judicial system, exerting control over the constitution of benches and the allocation of

⁵³ Shah, A, 'How Pakistan's Politicians Help the Military' (2020). The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/01/23/opinion/pakistan-politicians-military.html>

⁵⁴ Hussain A, 'Pakistan army chief admits military's meddling in politics' (2022) Aljazeera. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2022/11/23/pakistan-army-chief-vows-to-keep-military-out-of-politics>

⁵⁵ Sound Bites for Public, 'Former Chief Justice Nasim Hasan Shah explains judges are not that bold to sacrifice their jobs' (YouTube Video, Sound Bites for Public, 24 March 2022) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hfdaqxqbcfY>

cases to specific judges to get desired decisions.
 56

Hence, the military's persistent involvement in politics and the judiciary may have significantly weakened the system, promoting an environment favorable to financial corruption. Military interference in politics throughout Pakistan's history, even under civilian rule, has weakened public trust in the government institutions and threatened the foundations of democracy. Accountability and the rule of law are now under threat due to the military's potential to influence political results and damage the independence of the judiciary. Because the system's checks and balances are compromised and the interests of the powerful are prioritized, financial corruption can develop as a result of this systemic weakness.

These primary factors and challenges all work together to make Pakistan's corruption problem much worse than the UK's. The influence of influential people, the culture of corruption, the lack of funds and resources in government institutions, and the weakening of the rule of law all contribute significantly to the development of an atmosphere where corruption is pervasive. Addressing these factors and challenges is crucial to combat corruption effectively and promote transparency, accountability, and good governance in Pakistan.

4.6 Takeaways from U.K along with personal recommendations to reform the system in Pakistan: Britain's fight against corruption and eliminating it, consists of approximately 250 years. The lengthy and nonlinear process of combating corruption resulted in modern framework to combat corruption. The significant factors which lead Britain as least corrupt society are following;

1. Long-Term Process: Instead of a single transformative factor, anti-corruption efforts in Britain were the outcome of numerous moments of reform. This steady, long-term process lasted nearly 250 years.

⁵⁶ Tag T.V, "ISI is Involved in Manipulating Judicial Proceedings" - Justice Shaukat Aziz Siddiqui' (YouTube Video, Tag T.V, 22 July 2018) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wKx8N8IZ30>

2. Socio-Cultural Factors: Friendship, giving presents, familial ties, and favoritism were deeply rooted sociocultural practices that promoted corruption and the takeover of institutions. It took a lot of discussion and competition among the public to address these issues.

3. Public Pressure: Significant action against corruption was mostly sparked by public pressure and popular agitation. The public's urge to closely examine government spending was boosted by war, higher taxes, and moments of moral regeneration.

4. Role of Independent Press: The press in the Britain has played a vital role in changing the corruption system. With a relatively free press facilitating public debate and contestation, ethical concerns were raised and corruption exposed. The press served as a platform for whistleblowers and played a key role in holding individuals and institutions accountable. Formal mechanisms, such as national accounting bodies, worked alongside the press to strike a balance between trust and necessary distrust.

5. State-Formation: It took time and sometimes needed severe breaches of the allowed levels of profit to clearly define the border between public and private in Britain since the state was dependent on private agents to carry out its functions. East India Company and jails which were semi private, are prime examples.

6. Systems Approach: It was believed that corruption was a systemic problem, impacting several industries and interfering with other professions due to corrupt practices in one. The necessity for a comprehensive approach to fighting corruption rather than an isolated approach was emphasized by critics.

7. Trust and Distrust: It was vital to strike a balance between having faith in authorities and having the necessary distrust to check and limit abuse of power. Legal concepts of confidence and accountability changed over time and influenced norms in public life.

8. Political Support and Non-Partisan Solutions: Political support for nonpartisan

remedies, including commissions funded by the government, has been successful in advancing anti-corruption laws.

9. **Constant Reflection:** Continual reflection and vigilance are necessary for anti-corruption measures. History demonstrates that development is not necessarily linear and that, if moral standards and principles are not upheld, there is a possibility of return.⁵⁷

Subsequently, as mentioned above earlier and according to the World Justice Project, with its 14th position out of 140 countries, the UK stands out for its commendable protection of fundamental rights. It achieves this by prioritizing the preservation of freedoms, including those related to opinion, expression, belief, and religion as well as government officials in the executive, judicial, police, and military branches do not exploit public office for personal gain. Moreover, it ensures the right to life and security, equal treatment, and the absence of discrimination. Additionally, the UK places a strong emphasis on upholding due process of the law and safeguarding the rights of the accused.

On the basis of above facts and figure, following are the recommendations and takeaways from U.K that can help in improving the system in Pakistan;

1. **Long-Term Approach:** Adopt a thorough and continuous strategy to tackle corruption, drawing inspiration from the UK's long term efforts. Recognize that combating corruption needs a multifaceted approach that addresses the root reasons and introduces reforms gradually. Pakistan may successfully eradicate corruption and create a more open and responsible society by committing to long-term reforms.

2. **Political Support and Non-Partisan Solutions:** Pakistan can draw inspiration from the UK's successful approach of political support for non-partisan solutions in combating corruption. Similar to the UK, Pakistan should

prioritize non-partisan remedies, such as establishing independent commissions funded by the government. By adopting a non-partisan approach, Pakistan can effectively advance anti-corruption laws and initiatives, without being hindered by partisan interests. This commitment to non-partisan solutions will help Pakistan address corruption more comprehensively.

3. **Tackling Socio-Cultural Factors:** Analyze the UK's strategy for dealing with sociocultural practices that support corruption. Recognize and address Pakistan's prevailing problems, including as favoritism, family ties, and the tolerance of dishonest behavior. Encourage an environment of open discussion and constructive competition among people to question and modify these standards, promoting honesty and moral conduct.

4. **Public Pressure to change the system:** Being one of the major factor of “public pressure” in the UK's history to eliminate corruption, public pressure has the potential to play a significant role in driving change and reforming the corruption system in Pakistan. As the current economic and social situation in Pakistan continues to worsen, the increasing public pressure becomes even more crucial in demanding accountability and transparency from the government.

5. **Strengthening Oversight and Empowering the Press/media:** Recognize the essential role of a free and independent press in battling corruption, taking ideas from the UK's experience. In order to identify corruption and hold those responsible accountable, improve oversight procedures and support investigative journalists. In order to promote transparency and prevent corruption inside government institutions, support the establishment of strict freedom of information legislation and whistleblower protection. Pakistan may try to create a more open and responsible society by imitating the UK's dedication to press freedom and effective monitoring.

6. **Promoting Integrity and Preventing Abuse of Public Office:** As mentioned above, according to World Justice Project, Pakistan

⁵⁷ Whitty, B. ‘Trust and Distrust: Lessons about anti-corruption from Britain’s history’ (2022). University of Sussex. <https://blogs.sussex.ac.uk/centre-for-the-study-of-corruption/2022/04/29/trust-and-distrust-lessons-about-anti-corruption-from-britains-history/>

hold a significantly poor position when it comes to abuse of power by public officials, Pakistan must prioritize integrity and prevent government employees from abusing their positions for their own gain as a key lesson from the UK. To achieve this, anti-corruption policies must be strengthened and enforced at all levels of government, including the executive, judicial, police, and military. The ongoing struggle against corruption and the promotion of transparency and good governance in Pakistan can be considerably aided by Pakistan adopting the UK's dedication to prohibiting the use of public office for personal benefit.

7. Learn from History: Pakistan must consider the struggles and challenges faced by other countries, such as the UK, in the battle against corruption. Pakistan should research the long-term strategy used by the UK and modify it for its own setting, taking into consideration socio-cultural issues, public pressure, and a systems approach to fighting corruption.

8. International Cooperation: In order to effectively combat corruption, Pakistan should actively participate in international collaboration and exchange best practices with other countries. Working with international organizations and taking part in campaigns to fight corruption can offer helpful insights and assistance for putting into practice efficient anti-corruption measures.

9. Strengthen the rule of law: Focus on expertise and fixing structural issues in the legal and law enforcement systems as well as on strengthening the implementation and enforcement of current anti-corruption laws. Expertise in handling corruption cases should be developed through training programs and specialized units. Structural issues, such as bureaucratic hurdles and delays, should be identified and resolved to ensure efficient and timely processing of corruption cases. In order to ensure that corrupt behavior is constantly punished, organizations responsible for fighting corruption should become more effective.

10. Importance and promotion of transparency: The broad examination of facts, statistics, and cases mentioned above clearly

expose “lack of transparency” within the system of Pakistan. Transparency works as an essential tool in combating corruption, as it allows accountability, exposes wrongdoings, and promotes public trust in the government. Therefore, it is crucial to strengthen transparency measures in Pakistan to effectively combat corruption. By promoting openness, ensuring access to information, and enhancing accountability strategies, Pakistan can create a system that upholds transparency as a foundation in the fight against corruption.

11. Allocate Sufficient Resources: Make sure government agencies, particularly the police, have sufficient funding and resources to deter corruption and improve their abilities to combat it. To allow efficient law enforcement and protect the rule of law, invest in advanced facilities, advanced technology, and extensive training programs. The ability to investigate and prosecute corrupt people may be improved with enough resources, which will decrease the motivation for corruption and encourage openness and accountability.

12. Enhance Public Awareness and Engagement: It is crucial to raise public awareness of the damaging impacts of corruption and to promote a culture of intolerance for such behavior. Public engagement activities, civic education programs, and educational campaigns can assist rally support for the fight against corruption among the general population.

13. Strong implementation of existing laws: Strong anti-corruption laws may not be enough to solve the issue on its own. It is essential to make sure that Pakistan's anti-corruption legislation and regulations are correctly applied and enforced. It should be a top priority to strengthen the institutions in charge of fighting corruption, such as the National Accountability Bureau (NAB), and to improve their independence, efficacy, and transparency.

14. Building public trust and confidence: Combating corruption requires strengthening public confidence in governmental institutions. At all levels of government, including the

judicial system and police, transparency, accountability, and integrity should be encouraged. This may be accomplished by taking steps like promoting merit-based hiring, implementing strong code of conduct, increasing decision-making process, and promoting public engagement in governance.

15. Address the Culture of Corruption:

Use multiple approaches to combat a widespread corruption culture in Pakistani society. Prioritize the need for rehabilitation campaigns and programs in departments where pay and benefits are high yet corruption still exists in addition to increasing awareness about the negative impacts of corruption. Encourage a change in social norms that places an emphasis on moral conduct and integrity, cultivating a culture of responsibility and preventing the acceptability of corrupt practices in personal as well as professional life.

16. Strengthen Democracy and Limit Military Influence:

Prioritize strengthening democratic institutions, establishing civilian command over the armed forces, and reducing the influence of the military in politics and judicial system. Uphold democratic principles, transparency, and accountability to ensure civilian leaders have the authority and freedom to govern without interference. Additionally, measures should be taken to ensure the independence of the judiciary, free from external pressures, to guarantee fair and just decision-making. This will help create an environment where corruption is less likely to thrive and foster the rule of law.

4.7 Conclusion: In conclusion, the relevant legislation shows the presence of strict laws against financial corruption in Pakistan, just as in the UK. However, the implementation and enforcement of these laws in Pakistan are severely lacking, leading to a persistent problem of financial corruption. Despite having legislation in place primarily weak rule of law along with other factors such as inadequate funding, a lack of expertise, and structural issues within the legal and law enforcement systems hinder the effective application of anti-corruption measures.

Additionally, the low income and limited resources in government institutions, particularly the police, contribute to the openness of officials to engage in corrupt practices as a means to fill the income gap and fulfill departmental needs. The influence of influential individuals in Pakistan, who might manipulate institutions and exert pressure on government officials, creates an environment where corruption thrives. The deep-rooted culture of corruption, the historical involvement of the military in politics and the judiciary, and the resulting weakening of the system all is an outcome of weak implementation of law.

While strict laws are in place, their implementation is poor, primarily due to weak rule of also evident by reliable organizations. Addressing all these factors requires a comprehensive approach. Pakistan can draw lessons from the UK's experience in combating corruption, such as promoting non-partisan solutions, adopting a long-term strategy, strengthening oversight mechanisms and tackling socio-cultural factors.

Emphasizing the role of public pressure, promoting integrity and preventing abuse of public office, international cooperation, empowering the press and media, learning from history, allocation of sufficient resources, addressing the culture of corruption, enhancing public awareness and engagement, building public trust and confidence, and strengthening democracy while limiting military influence are also crucial for reforming the system in Pakistan. In conclusion, while Pakistan possesses strict laws against financial corruption, their poor implementation remains the primary cause of the widespread corruption. Addressing the implementation gap, along with other factors such as low income and resources, is essential to effectively combat corruption, promote transparency, and ensure good governance in Pakistan.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all my lecturers and professors who have played a significant role in my academic journey. Their knowledge, guidance, and support have been invaluable throughout my LLM program. I am truly thankful for their dedication to imparting

knowledge and shaping my understanding of the subject matter.

In particular, I would like to extend a special thanks to Dr. Lars Mosesson for his exceptional guidance and mentorship during the process of writing this dissertation. His expertise and insightful feedback have been instrumental in shaping this research and pushing me to achieve my best. Dr. Mosesson's commitment to excellence and his ability to provide valuable guidance have truly made a difference in the quality and depth of this work.

Lastly, I would like to thank my family and friends for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout this journey. Their belief in me and their constant motivation have been the driving force behind my perseverance and determination.

REFERENCES

- GEORGIEVA, K. 'Fighting corruption: the importance is crystal clear' (2018) World Bank Blogs. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/voices/fighting-corruption-importance-crystal-clear>
- Jamali, M. 'Anti-Corruption' United Nations Global Compact. <https://unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/our-work/governance/anti-corruption>
- Aqil, M. 'The cancer of corruption in Pakistan' (2023) Pakistan Observer. <https://pakobserver.net/the-cancer-of-corruption-in-pakistan-by-tariq-aqil/>
- Transparency International UK 'Corruption and UK' Transparency International UK <https://www.transparency.org.uk/corruption-and-uk>
- Ryan, E. 'Research Objectives | Definition & Examples' (2022) Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/research-process/research-objectives/#:~:text=about%20research%20objectives-.What%20is%20a%20research%20objective%3F,end%20of%20your%20problem%20statement.>
- Prevention of Corruption Act, 1947 (Act No. II of 1947) https://ace.punjab.gov.pk/system/files/THE_PREVENTION_OF_CORRUPTION_ACT_1947.pdf
- Wikipedia, 'National Accountability Bureau' Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Accountability_Bureau
- National Accountability Bureau Ordinance 1999 (NAB Ordinance), No. XIX of 1999. <https://nab.gov.pk/Downloads/nao.asp>
- Federal Investigation Agency, 'Anti-Corruption Wing Mandate' Federal Investigation Agency. <https://fia.gov.pk/acw#:~:text=%C3%97-.Field%20Formation,government%20public%20servants%20and%20funds.>
- Sadiq, E. 'Anti-Corruption investigation agencies in Pakistan' (2020). <https://issrapapers.ndu.edu.pk/site/article/view/51/26>
- Ibid
- Aga Faquir Mohammad & Co. 'BENAMI TRANSACTIONS LAWS IN PAKISTAN' (2023). Pakistan Lawyers. <https://pakistanlawyer.com/articles/story/benami-transaction-laws-in-pakistan>
- Dow Jones. 'What is United Kingdom Bribery Act?' Dow Jones. <https://www.dowjones.com/professional/risk/glossary/anti-bribery-corruption/uk-bribery-act/>
- Bribery Act, 2010. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/23/contents>
- Morton, M. 'Criminal Finances Act 2017: Failure to prevent facilitation of tax evasion' (2022). Mercia. <https://www.mercia-group.com/mercia-news-and-blog/criminal-finances-act-2017/#:~:text=The%20Criminal%20Finances%20Act%20came,from%20criminally%20facilitating%20tax%20evasion.>
- Smyth, E. 'Criminal Finances Act 2017' (2017) Kingsley Napley. <https://www.kingsleynapley.co.uk/insights/blogs/criminal-law-blog/criminal-finances-act-2017>
- Counter Fraud Services. 'The Fraud Act (2006)' HSC Counter Fraud and Probity Services. <https://cfps.hscni.net/information/the-fraud-act/>
- Fraud Act 2006. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2006/35/contents>

- ID Now. 'Proceeds of Crime Act (POCA)' ID Now.
<https://www.idnow.io/glossary/proceeds-of-crime-act-poca/#:~:text=The%20Proceeds%20of%20Crime%20Act%20allows%20for%20the%20confiscation%20of,indirectly%20derived%20from%20criminal%20activity.>
- Binns, J. 'A Simple Guide to the Law on Money Laundering under the Proceeds of Crime Act 2002' (2021) BCL Solicitors LLP.
https://www.bcl.com/a-simple-guide-to-the-law-on-money-laundering-under-the-proceeds-of-crime-act-2002/?utm_source=mondaq&utm_medium=syndication&utm_term=Criminal-Law&utm_content=articleoriginal&utm_campaign=article
- Trading Economics. 'Pakistan Corruption Rank' Trading Economics.
<https://tradingeconomics.com/pakistan/corruption-rank>
- Ahmed, A. 'Pakistan's corruption score worst in a decade: report' (2023). The express Tribune.
<https://tribune.com.pk/story/2398583/pakistan-s-corruption-score-worst-in-a-decade-report>
- Duncan, G. 'UK falls to its lowest ranking on global corruption index' (2023). The National News.
<https://www.thenationalnews.com/world/uk-news/2023/01/31/uk-falls-to-its-lowest-ranking-on-global-corruption-index/>
- Lawson, A. 'UK drops down global corruption index after string of scandals' (2023). The Guardian.
<https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2023/jan/31/uk-global-corruption-index-transparency-international-qatar-russia-brazil>
- Jolly, J. 'Pakistani tycoon agrees to hand over £190m to UK authorities' (2019) The Guardian.
<https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2019/dec/03/pakistani-tycoon-malik-riaz-hussain-hands-over-pounds-190m-to-uk-authorities-nca>
- The Nation. 'Al-Qadir Trust case - a timeline' (2023) The Nation.
<https://www.nation.com.pk/09-May-2023/al-qadir-trust-case-a-timeline>
- Hamid Yusufzai, 'LEAKED Planted Interview Of Malik Riaz With Mehar Bukhari And Mubashir LuQman on Dunya TV FULL' (YouTube Video, Hamid Yusufzai, 14 June 2012)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ME2YirSD5cA>
- Future Investments, 'Malik Riaz Exclusive Interview with Saleem safi' (YouTube Video, Future Investments, 26 December 2018)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wwWmwNFoQtQ>
- Abbasi, A. 'Police and judiciary most corrupt institutions, says TI Pakistan' (2021) The news International.
<https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/915055-police-and-judiciary-most-corrupt-institutions-says-ti-pakistan>
- The express Tribune. 'Police, judiciary top most corrupt in Pakistan' (2022) The Express Tribune.
<https://tribune.com.pk/story/2390359/police-judiciary-top-most-corrupt-in-pakistan-survey>
- Geo-Fact Check. 'Fact-check: What are the salaries, benefits of the Supreme Court judges?' (2023) Geo TV.
<https://www.geo.tv/latest/480211-fact-check-what-are-the-salaries-benefits-of-the-supreme-court-judges>
- World Justice Project. 'Pakistan' (2022). World Justice Project.
<https://worldjusticeproject.org/rule-of-law-index/country/2022/Pakistan/>
- Pakistan Lawyer. 'Why is Pakistan's judiciary system different for rich and poor' (2021). Pakistan Lawyer, access to Justice.
<https://pakistanlawyer.com/articles/story/why-is-pakistan-s-judiciary-system-different-for-rich-and-poor>
- Human Rights Watch. 'The Crooked System, Police abuse and reforms in Pakistan' (2016). Human Rights Watch
https://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/report_pdf/pakistan0916_web.pdf

- World Justice Project. 'United Kingdom' (2022). WJP Rule of Law Index. <https://worldjusticeproject.org/rule-of-law-index/country/2022/United%20Kingdom/>
- Pakistan & Gulf Economist. 'Cronyism and Corruption in Pakistan's Political and Economic Landscape' (2023). Pakistan & Gulf Economist. <https://www.pakistangulfeconomist.com/2023/03/19/cronyism-and-corruption-in-pakistans-political-landscape/>
- Naseer, T. 'Former PM Raja Pervez Ashraf acquitted in Sahiwal Rental Power Project case' (2020). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1565158>
- Fazal, S. 'Rental Power Plant case: Acquittal plea of all accused to be decided together' (2022). Business Recorder. <https://www.brecorder.com/news/40168563/rental-power-plant-case-acquittal-plea-of-all-accused-to-be-decided-together>
- The Express Tribune. 'Ashraf gets relief in six more RPP cases' (2022). The Express Tribune. <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2376472/ashraf-gets-relief-in-six-more-rpp-cases>
- Asad, M. 'Hajj corruption case: Former federal minister sentenced to 16 years in prison' (2016). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1262506>
- Chaudhry, W. 'Former religious affairs minister acquitted in Hajj corruption case' (2017). Daily Times. <https://dailytimes.com.pk/22150/former-religious-affairs-minister-acquitted-in-hajj-corruption-case/>
- Dawn News. 'How the high-profile Ogra scam became a 'complicated' case' (2016). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1251360>
- Asad, M. 'NAB challenges acquittal of ex-PMs, others in Ogra chairman's appointment case' (2022). Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1685905>
- The News International. 'PPP's Amin Fahim among 11 indicted in NICL scam case' (2015). The News International. <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/14621-ppps-amin-fahim-among-11-indicted-in-nicl-scam-case>
- The express Tribune. 'Ex-NICL chief, 5 others jailed over Rs490m corruption' (2018). The Express Tribune. <https://tribune.com.pk/story/1862685/former-chairman-five-others-imprisoned-nicl-corruption-case>
- Daily Times. 'AC acquits former NICL head, co-accused in corruption case' (2020). Daily Times. <https://dailytimes.com.pk/533307/ac-acquits-former-nicl-head-co-accused-in-corruption-case/#:~:text=An%20accountability%20court%20on%20Saturday,tune%20of%20billions%20of%20rupees.>
- World Justice Project. 'Pakistan' (2022). World Justice Project. <https://worldjusticeproject.org/rule-of-law-index/country/2022/Pakistan/>
- Malik, N, 'A Study of Economic, Cultural, and Political Causes of Police Corruption in Pakistan' (2020). Oxford Academic. <https://academic.oup.com/policing/article/15/2/1446/5840664>
- Abbas, H, 'Police & Law Enforcement Reform in Pakistan: Crucial for Counterinsurgency and Counterterrorism Success' (2009). GSDRC. <https://gsdrc.org/document-library/police-law-enforcement-reform-in-pakistan-crucial-for-counterinsurgency-and-counterterrorism-success/>
- Staff Report, 'Inadequate resources affecting Punjab Police performance' (2022). Daily Times. <https://dailytimes.com.pk/1013840/inadequate-resources-affecting-punjab-police-performance/>
- Warraich, S, 'Resource starved' (2020). The News. <https://www.thenews.com.pk/tns/detail/603488-resource-starved>
- Shah, A, 'How Pakistan's Politicians Help the Military' (2020). The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/01/23/opinion/pakistan-politicians-military.html>
- Hussain A, 'Pakistan army chief admits military's meddling in politics' (2022) Aljazeera. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2022/1/23/pakistans-army-chief-vows-to-keep-military-out-of-politics>

Sound Bites for Public, 'Former Chief Justice Nasim Hasan Shah explains judges are not that bold to sacrifice their jobs' (YouTube Video, Sound Bites for Public, 24 March 2022)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hfdagxqbcfY>

Tag T.V, "ISI is Involved in Manipulating Judicial Proceedings" - Justice Shaukat Aziz Siddiqui' (YouTube Video, Tag T.V,

22 July 2018)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wKx8N8IZ30>

Whitty, B. 'Trust and Distrust: Lessons about anti-corruption from Britain's history' (2022). University of Sussex. <https://blogs.sussex.ac.uk/centre-for-the-study-of-corruption/2022/04/29/trust-and-distrust-lessons-about-anti-corruption-from-britains-history/>.

